

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: WAZIRI****FIRST NAME: MUHAMMAD AWWAL****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show essential information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10)

List your seven critical concepts with the page number in-text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. **Introduction**
2. **The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)**
3. **Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13)**
4. **Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers (EUCLID 2019, 14-16)**
5. **Literature Review (EUCLUD 2019, 17-23)**
6. **Writing Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 25-26)**
7. **American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)**
8. **Corrections to Papers (EUCLID 2019, 36-43)**
9. **Conclusion**
10. **References**

THE ESSENTIAL BUILDING BLOCKS FOR ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The revised coursepack ACA-401D (2019) for period one presents a holistic and concise summary of essay writing's basic styles for academic purposes. Bow Valley College (2020) states, "An essay is a "short formal piece of writing...dealing with a single subject." The coursepack presented a roadmap for doctoral academic writing, explaining that an academic essay intends to answer a question or task to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence. The coursepack highlighted the steps to essay writing, including the initial plan's assignment, referencing, and careful editing to improve the essay by ensuring logical flow (EUCLID 20219, 1- 2).

Chapters 2-4 discussed the ethics of writing, plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5) in Cookmyproject (n.d.), "taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author."

Accordingly, the coursepack stated if a paragraph goes on for more than 20 lines, find a way to divide it up; if your paper falls into sections, make sure to include a sentence or two connective tissue between the areas (EUCLID 2019, 24). Moreover, put things as thoroughly as you can. As discussed in the coursepack, essay writing's niceties by highlighting 11 essential things to remember and punctuation and correct grammar have been well established and straightforward. Still, the style is much more than just proper punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary (ibid.). The coursepack discussed the fundamental differences between American and British English, so uniformity is maintained throughout the write-up, looking at pronunciation, punctuation, spellings, grammar, syntax, and general use. While "Turabian style" was referenced, this is simply the Chicago style applied to research papers. Revised Fall 2006 (EUCLID 2019, 44). It detailed out Chicago style and its use, the page formatting, and end/footnotes.

2) THE BASICS OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

I started writing a response paper with lots of apprehensions because it is a Ph.D. program. The demand and effort required are enormous. It is a distance learning program, and it is quite some time since an institution engaged me in earnest academic work. With trepidation and questions in mind, I started ACA-401D with the designated coursepack and video on rules of style for a Response Paper (RP). These essential tools are critical for questioning, developing a thesis and research topic, analyses, and results in the dissertation's presentation. They can be useful to apply in my daily work from now on.

The coursepack presented the structure of writing essays and the critical necessary steps to follow. However, the coursepack stressed that even though there are essential steps to writing a paper, it is not necessarily a linear process. You might work through the different stages in writing an essay (EUCLID 2019, 1-2). The first thing to do is start preparations early, define the problem, and develop a plan to proceed. Next, you need to research and read widely by taking notes and organizing ideas to build a knowledge base on the subject matter, understanding the work done, and where the gaps could inform your research (ibid.).

3) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is a severe academic offense to guard against by all research students and academia. As discussed, "Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information (EUCLID 2019, 5)."

The coursepack also highlighted some important things to note regarding avoiding plagiarism by appropriate citing and quotations. When not to cite to show originality and when the information is general knowledge, the coursepack provided the citation and referencing format and how to achieve logical flow. Kate Miller-Wilson (Your Dictionary.com) provided 12 different types of plagiarism to avoid, which constitutes a literary fraud with severe consequences. Kaveh *et al.* (2014) in International Education

Series published a paper on ethical and unethical plagiarism prevention methods in academic writing.

They classified plagiarism into two groups of authors with plagiarism. For the first group of authors who are aware of plagiarism, the only solution is to provide them with sufficient education on the consequences of ethical and unethical writings. The second group includes the authors who plagiarize unconsciously without any intention to do so. Accordingly, two effective methods to cover up plagiarism by these two authors: 1) Unethical practices, 2) Ethical procedures.

4) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

Chapter three of the coursepack provided useful suggestions for the doctoral student to improve essay writing. I find these suggestions apt in providing increased impetus to the essay. The student needs to state the thesis at the beginning or near and personalize it if needed, and if you don't have one, get it. There is a need to explain the theory in the thesis and avoid generality, be specific to avoid suspicion, and write clearly in terms of sentence structure, paragraphs, quotations, and citations (EUCLID 2019, 14-16). The serious student is discussing and avoiding plagiarism to maintain the essay and writer's integrity and accountability.

5) LITERATURE REVIEW

The coursepack has been explicit in explaining some of the mistakes that happen when students write and gave clear explanations and examples to avoid ambiguities. Some fundamental rules were given that helps to prevent confusion and make great write-ups. I am genuinely excited for this excellent learning opportunity because I have been guilty of mismatches, confusion, and outright mix-up, especially contractions and possessives. For instance, the use of "its" and "it's" benefits of "your" and "you're" and the difference between "that" precedes only restrictive phrases in contrast "which" usually precedes nonrestrictive words, when should one use "I" versus "me," and can one start using a sentence with "and." The use of a comma before "and" was detailed with examples for clarity (EUCLID 2019, 18-20).

6) WRITING STYLE AND HOW TO USE IT

A writing technique is a style an author uses to convey their message in a manner that is effective and meaningful to their audience (EUCLID 2019, 24). Understanding the different writing techniques is essential to professionals because you will need to change your writing style to connect with your audience.

Euclid University recommends the use of Chicago Rules (Turabian), but other internationally recognized rules are acceptable. The style guide stressed the need to be

consistent depending on writing, like academic writing, technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting (EUCLID 2019, 24). Guidelines are usually published to allow more than one author to contribute while ensuring that the finished product does not necessarily carry the writer's style but the publication, company, or website associated with the writing.

Depending on the nature of the writing and the intended audience, the four main types of essays for use by writers (Indeed Career Development, 2020) the descriptive, narrative, persuasive, and expository as follows:

Descriptive writing immerses the reader into a story by creating a vivid picture of characters, settings, and events in their mind. The illustrative writing style aims to make the reader feel like they are experiencing the possibilities for themselves. Narrative writing expands upon the descriptive writing style and tells an entire story with a beginning, middle, and end. Persuasive essays convince or influence the reader to believe or do what the writer wants them to do. The style uses logical reasoning with an emotional connection that persuades the reader to adopt the writer's personal opinions and beliefs. Expository writing to inform, explain, or describe something to the reader.

The use of punctuation and correct grammar is well established and straightforward, but the style is much more than just the proper usage of punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary. Accordingly, the coursepack outlined many different aspects to consider, such as preferred sentence length, manuscript layout, font usage, through to the use of headings, lists, and trademark or branding considerations (EUCLID 2019, 24 - 25).

7) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

The student needs to understand the fundamental differences between American and British English. The doctoral academic write-up will be consistent with the rules of engagement in writing for educational purposes. According to the British Council Foundation Indonesia (n.d.).

The coursepack discussed pronunciation, although same spelling; different spelling, although same pronunciation; same words, but other or additional meanings; grammar, syntax, punctuation, general usage; same concept, further terms or expressions; or same story, different in style, connotation or frequency, and many other significant differences to note (EUCLID 2019, 27-29).

8) CORRECTIONS TO PAPERS

This chapter of the coursepack discussed the writing niceties that the student needs to observe, such as respecting the formatting of the response papers, quizzes, and essential papers to avoid disrupting the Euclid University's established convention. It teaches the student choice and placement of words, when to use a period, when to start a new paragraph, and talks to create the section. The coursepack owes to avoid the use of

"serious" in academic papers because things are always "serious." Instead, use "threatening" or "unsettling (EUCLID 2019, 36-39).

9) CONCLUSION

This response paper is my first step in pursuing a doctorate in Global Public Health, and Health Systems (PHGH) is a fruitful experience to read the ACA-401D period one and dwell on the coursepack and orientation documents to watching the videos presented by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck.

This course has started to polish my language and writing skills because I can now use Grammarly and Zotero to improve my write-ups and do appropriate referencing. I am getting excited that I have made the right decision to join Euclid University to fulfill my ambition of pursuing a doctorate in global health. It will help my work on facts and evidence. The use of Grammarly will help me learn how to cite, paraphrase, and quote without plagiarism. I will follow the writing format and style strictly according to Euclid's checklist for papers and Turabian style.

The coursepack initially made me nervous because of its structure, but I am beginning to appreciate the content and the lessons therein after going through it carefully. The first response paper had been a severe struggle, but it taught me some lessons that I will apply to progress with my study without much problems.

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